

EFFICACY IN ENHANCING ESSAY WRITING OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH DIGITAL MEDIA

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Abstract:

The existing paper deals with improving essay writing through a digital way. The lockdown situation taught lot of things in a common man life. Students are the one who was affected in this period. They forgot lots of skills. Especially, writing skill. Digital world helps the students to get touch with the teacher and education. They learn their classes through audio, video and slides. They travelled far away from writings. Writing alone help a person to keep the thoughts or ideas in long term memory. The important part to promote education is writings. Writings rectify our errors, improve our ideas and project our thoughts clear. Our words will live after our death only through writings. Many leaders are still alive through their writings. Our valuable writings improve our self and the future generation. This paper is an attempt to make the student realise the importance of writing skill and to enhance their writing skill. There are varieties of writing skill. The researcher has chosen essay writing to improve learners writing and their academics. The researcher used digital media as the tool to enhance their skills. Print, apps, websites, audio, video, recordings and digital writing comes under digital world. Our contemporary world is digitalised. From dawn to dusk human revolves around the digital world. So, the researcher uses that digital media for education purpose. It helps the student to enjoy and learn their skills.

Key Words: Essay Writing, Digital Media, App Assisted Learning

1. Introduction:

The present world revolves around English language. It shows the influence in cooking till artificial intelligence. To develop that language four skills are important Writing skill, Reading skill, Listening Skill and speaking skill. The most significant skill is writing skill. The language is alive only through the writings. There are lots of writing skills, Essay writing, poetry writing, content writing and academic writing. This paper deals about essay writing. Essay writing is one of the important parts for learners to develop their writing skills. Essay writing means a general piece of writing. The single subject or idea discussed in detailed note. It is near to research writing. Essay must have a good opening with sharp and smart quotes, introduction about the subject; present the ideas with good examples and expressing the thoughts to support the points and reasons, finally a concluding part with a good proverb or quote. Essay writing is equal to research writing. Without secondary source and creative thoughts essay writing will not be fulfilled. Digital media is used as a tool to enhance essay writing. Digital media become as a God to contemporary world. Everything in our world becomes digitalised. Digitalisation is a communication from one person to universe. Digital media preserves all our information in electronics. Nothing can be easily erased in digital world. It can retrieve if we lost all the things. Information's are widely spread over the world through digital media. Human can access anything in any part of the world. Learners can show their talents to the world inside the four walls. Digital media creates lots way to develop learner's knowledge. This paper discusses about writing skills especially essay writing with the help of digital media. The enhancement of writing skills helps a learner to improve lots of skills and knowledge.

2. Enhancing Essay Writing through Digital Media:

The present paper aim is to enhance writing skills (essay writing) through Digital media. Digital media contains audio, video, print media, software, web pages, video games, recordings, databases etc.,. These sources help the learners and researcher to complete the study. These sources are the big support for all the research scholars and new learners to create their path for future. App Assisted learning is the approach used for the present study. Digital media alone has the power to entertain as well as give information. Digital media has the power to give archaic information to technological information. Learners show their interest on different branches of digital media. Essay writing with digital media brings out the students new idea and learners tries to see every old thing in new perspectives.

3. Purpose of the Study:

The purpose of the study is to enhance essay writing skill for higher secondary school students with the help of digital media. Writings (digital or writing) documented the facts, ideas and emotions. It documents past, present and future. Each and every single piece of work is prominent to the world. Learners have lots of knowledge to read, listen, speak and write. Learners have the capacity to write a lot but they did not know what prefers most? How to write? and What to write? . Learners have lots of question before writing. They have lots of expression and emotion about a subject but they did not have a proper guidance to reflect their emotions. To

regulate the writings and to promote the ideas of learners digital media is significant. For this study lots of source is used. Learners have the liberation to choose their own source for their writing. It can be in any form audio, video, recordings, clippings, photography's anything under the sky in digital platform. These sources are the pillars to improve their essay writing. This digital world will also bring the archaic world through the writings. The researcher attempts to enhance learners essay writing skill through digital media.

4. Objectives

- To improve writing skills
- To improve learners content in writings.
- To introduce lots of sources for writings.
- To create interest towards essay writing.
- To improve their reading skill.
- To improve their creativity in writings.

5. Approach:

The present study uses App Assisted Learning (AAL) approach. This pandemic situation promotes AAL approach. Learners did not have a study centre to learn in this situation. Online apps become as the study platform for learners. Nowadays, Group discussions, conference and debates become natural in online. App Assisted learning allows lots of people and facts to our circle. Learners not only learn the optimistic idea of subject but they can learn pessimistic view of their specific subject. It helps the learners to analyse their ideas. Lots of apps are promoted. Each and every app has a unique way and it gives the standard facts. Apps are not idea of single man. It gives lots of legends opinion about the subject. Learners can choose any app for their study. They can take any convenient apps to use or get their facts. In AAL, it gives the merits and demerits of source and also its data bases. Apps not only used academic purpose, it also use for household, business and other personal purposes. This study connects with lots of sources and different apps. This study deals with three elements:

- **Content:** Our digital world has lots of content. Learner has to choose their content for the writings. They also have to select the app which is related to content. Source from the app must support and promote the content for essay writing.
- **Process:** Learners have lots of process before essay writing. They have to read lots of secondary sources and have to note down important facts. They have order the ideas in writings. They have to mention both merits and demerits of the writings. They must have the valid reasons and examples to support their essay (specific topic). They have to make a rough draft.
- **Outcomes:** The rough draft helps the learner to make fair draft. Rough draft gives the clear picture about the work of learner. Students use rough draft as their primary source and bring out a wonderful essay art. The outcome brings the best essay of the student.
- Thus, the element discussed for the study.

6. Identification of the Problem:

Pandemic situation has changed many cycles in human life. Lots of people become lazy. Many people started to forget their lot of skills. They are not able to practice some skills. In such way students are started to forget their writing skills. They are not spending their times in writing. Student listen the recorded classes in their convenient time. Making of notes habit started to slow down in the student cycle. Writing is more significant to the learners. It alone store in long time memory of the student what they read, listen or saw. In pandemic situation, many children forgot to write, especially essay writing. Essay writing is also one of the academic purposes. The researcher took problem for the study. The researcher tries to develop digital essay writing for the learners with the help of digital media. The technological aid used for the study is mobiles and laptops. The researcher gives lots of liberation to learners to bring out their expression and facts. The researcher tries to shape their idea to essay.

7. Methodology:

The researcher selected two groups from higher secondary school for the study. Nearly thirty sessions were held for the present study.

- **Ice Breaking Session:** The researcher made one to one conversation with students to know their interests. It also creates a bond between learner and researcher. The researcher always has a thought that the friendly bond between learner and guide alone helps for the success.
- **Pre - Test:** The researcher conducted the pre-test to analyse the students attitude towards essay writing.
- **Classes:** The class held with the support of digital media. The researcher gave the liberation to select the topic. Learners must have to discuss about the topic and sources to the researcher. They also have to support their emotions with ideas. They must have to bring any new facts in their topics. Simple rough draft must send to the researcher before the fair draft. Rough drafts also discussed and analysed between the learner and the researcher.

- **Continuous Assessment Test:** The CAT is conducted to note down the learners improvement. CAT is analysed on the basis of content, grammar, creativity, reasons and examples.
- **Post- test:** After the session, post-test was conducted. Post- test was conducted to both groups to identify whether this study will applicable for learners or not.

8. Findings of the Study:

Two groups were selected to analyse the study. The mean value (post- test) of control group is 8.2. The experimental group mean value is 13.5. The difference between the control group and experimental group is 5.3. The graphical representation favors the experimental group.

9. Conclusion:

From the results, it found that digital media helps as a big tool for essay writing. It also supports other writings. Writings only documents emotions, expression, culture, facts and ideas. Writings bring good memory. Writing develops knowledge of human, standard of language and pride of country.

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